

Decarbonized Steel Production with Novel Processes

D3.1

Refining boundaries of the CLpre process

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Abstract	<p>The transition toward low-carbon steel-making demands innovative reduction technologies to re-place the conventional blast furnace route. The utilization of hydrogen or mixtures of hydrogen and carbon monoxide in the syngas-based reduction of iron ores is recognized as a viable pathway to reduce CO₂ emissions significantly. Fluidized bed reactors offer some advantages, including high heat and mass transfer rates, while eliminating the need for energy-intensive agglomeration steps, such as pelletizing. This report provides an insight into the process design and reactor configuration for the chemical looping pre-heating and pre-reduction (CLpre) process using biomass waste and iron ore as an oxygen carrier, with particular focus on expectable thermodynamic driving forces and kinetic behavior of reduction reactions of iron oxides. The technology has been discussed as a method of supplying the required process heat for iron ore pre-heating, pre-reducing iron oxides and enabling efficient CO₂ capture to generate negative emissions.</p>
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Executive Summary

Fluidized bed reactors offer some advantages, including high heat and mass transfer rates, while eliminating the need for energy-intensive agglomeration steps, such as pelletizing. This report provides an insight into the process design and reactor configuration for the chemical looping pre-heating and pre-reduction (CLpre) process using biomass waste as fuel and iron ore as an oxygen carrier, with particular focus on expectable thermodynamic driving forces and kinetic behavior of reduction reactions of iron oxides. The technology has been discussed as a method of supplying the required process heat for iron ore pre-heating, pre-reducing iron oxides and enabling efficient CO₂ capture to generate negative emissions.

Two main findings can be extracted from the investigations carried out in the course of the deliverable:

- It can be concluded that hematite is most likely to be reduced to magnetite during the CLpre process, which results in a reduction degree of approx. 11%. Further reduction to wüstite may be theoretically possible, but seems to be unlikely.
- For the CLpre process and the expected achievable reduction degrees, the available amount of reducing gas is most likely the limiting step during ore reduction in the fuel reactor, which operates as a typical bubbling bed under atmospheric pressure.

Future investigations of the process concept will focus on the mass and energy balance of the CLpre process within the identified limitations with regard to thermodynamics.

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1 Introduction

The global iron and steel industry is undergoing a significant transformation in process technology, particularly due to increasing environmental compliance requirements, rising the need to reduce process-related CO₂ emissions. As one of the most carbon-intensive industrial production sectors, steelmaking accounts for about 7-9% of global anthropogenic CO₂ emissions. The conventional blast furnace method, based on the reduction of iron ore with coke, remains the dominant method of metallic iron production, but is also a major source of these emissions due to its reliance on carbon-based reducing agents and high-temperature combustion processes. In response to the climate targets, direct reduction (DR) technologies have gained increasing relevance as alternatives to conventional iron-making. These processes utilize gaseous reducing agents, primarily hydrogen or hydrogen and carbon monoxide mixture to convert iron oxides into metallic iron. The resulting direct reduced iron (DRI) can be melted in electric arc furnaces. Commercial implementations such as MIDREX process employ shaft furnaces and reformed natural gas to achieve high metallization levels in pelletized ore feedstocks. Compared to traditional routes, such configurations significantly reduce CO₂ emissions per ton of crude steel. A further reduction in carbon intensity can be achieved by using hydrogen as a reducing gas. When hydrogen is produced via electrolysis using low-carbon electricity, the only gaseous by-product of the reduction reaction is water vapor. This eliminates direct CO₂ emissions from the reduction stage and aligns with strategic decarbonization pathways. Reactor configuration and process design are critical determinants of performance and scalability in hydrogen-based iron ore reduction. Among these, fluidized bed reactors offer some process advantages, including high heat and mass transfer rates, uniform temperature and good gas–solid contact. These systems are particularly suitable for the reduction of fine iron ores and eliminate the need for energy-intensive agglomeration steps. However, ultrafine particles have a tendency to agglomerate in the reactor or are entrained and carried out of the fluidized bed system. Circored process is a benchmark technology for the fluidized bed reduction of fine iron ores. However, due to the elevated temperatures at which hydrogen direct reduction takes place, a significant amount of energy is consumed by the unavoidable preheating of the iron ore. Due to economic considerations, the simple thermal utilization of hydrogen for preheating seems to be unfavorable. Thus, sustainable biomass waste utilization offers a promising option for preheating.

Benchmark technology- Circored

Circored is a hydrogen-based direct reduction technology developed to process fine iron ores [1]. The process is implemented through a two-stage fluidized bed reactor system. The initial pre-reduction step takes place in a circulating fluidized bed (CFB) followed by final reduction in a bubbling fluidized bed (BFB). In the first step, the iron ore is preheated to approximately 850 °C and undergoes partial reduction within the CFB reactor. The pre-reduced material is then transferred to the BFB reactor, which operates at approximately 650 °C under lower gas velocities. The BFB stage provides a longer residence time, allowing for completion of the reduction reaction and achieving high reduction degrees. The hydrogen is typically generated via steam reforming in combination with shift reaction and CO₂ removal units and serves as the exclusive reductant. Due to the moderate temperature regime in the final reduction step, the produced DRI must be reheated before the hot briquetting step. Alternatively, the reduced iron ore fines can be fed directly into an electric arc furnace for subsequent melting. The preheating is typically conducted with natural gas, which results in a significant carbon footprint. A schematic overview of the Circored process is provided in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Simplified process flow diagram of Circored process [2]

In the context of ironmaking, chemical looping combustion (CLC) concepts are being considered toward chemical looping pre-heating and pre-reduction, in which iron ore is reduced using syngas in a dual-reactor system, offering the potential for integrated CO₂ capture and utilization. These

innovative reactor configurations represent a promising direction for sustainable iron ore reduction processes.

2 Chemical looping combustion

The chemical looping combustion (CLC) process is based on a dual-reactor configuration that consists of a fuel reactor (FR) and an air reactor (AR) operated as fluidized beds [3,4]. These reactors are thermochemically coupled via a circulating solid oxygen carrier, typically a metal oxide, which facilitates redox reactions without direct contact between fuel and air. In the fuel reactor, the oxygen carrier oxidizes the incoming fuel by transferring its lattice oxygen, generating a CO₂- and H₂O-rich gas stream and simultaneously reducing the metal oxide. This technology has been widely studied and reviewed in the context of energy conversion and CO₂ capture applications [5-7].

The main reactions involved in the CLC process include:

1. Oxidation of the oxygen carrier in the air reactor:

2. Oxidation of the fuel by the oxygen carrier in the fuel reactor:

3. Oxidation of reducing gases (CO and H₂) by the oxygen carrier:

4. Steam reforming of hydrocarbons:

5. Water-gas shift reaction:

The reduced oxygen carrier is subsequently transferred to the air reactor, where it undergoes reoxidation in an exothermic reaction with air. The regenerated carrier is then recycled to the fuel reactor, enabling continuous cyclic operation of the system. This indirect oxidation mechanism enhances thermal efficiency, minimizes energy losses and facilitates CO₂ separation from the product gas stream.

The selection of appropriate oxygen carrier materials is critical to process performance and typically includes metal oxides such as those based on iron, nickel, copper or manganese [8]. These materials are evaluated based on oxygen transport capacity, redox kinetics, thermal and mechanical stability and environmental compatibility. A schematic overview of the chemical looping combustion process and its reactor configuration is provided in Fig.2.

Fig. 2 Principles of chemical looping combustion (CLC)

Iron oxides are of particular interest, as they simultaneously serve as oxygen carriers and reducible feedstock. The redox reactions between the fuel and air reactors occur due to a strong chemical potential gradient, making the process thermodynamically favorable and conducive to efficient heat integration. In ironmaking applications, this reactor system can be adapted to allow pre-heating and pre-reduction of iron oxides.

3 Chemical looping pre-heating and pre-reduction (CLpre)

In chemical looping-based pre-reduction (CLpre) for ironmaking, the system is configured to enable both preheating and partial reduction of iron oxides. Iron ore serves as both the reactive oxygen carrier and the reducible feedstock. The process consists of two interconnected fluidized bed reactors: the fuel reactor, where hematite reacts with reducing gases such as CO and H₂ and the air reactor, where the partially reduced material is reoxidized with air in an exothermic reaction. This redox cycling facilitates both stepwise reduction of the iron oxide and thermal energy recovery, as the heat released in the AR is used to preheat the incoming solids. In the FR, the gas-phase composition dynamically evolves due to additional reforming and water–gas shift reactions, further influencing reduction efficiency. The resulting flue gas, composed primarily of CO₂ and H₂O, is inherently suitable for CO₂ capture as it avoids nitrogen dilution typically associated with conventional combustion systems. The overall performance of the CLpre system is governed by parameters such as reactor temperature, gas composition, solid residence time and oxygen carrier properties. An additional benefit of the CLpre process is the possibility of introducing iron ore into a reducing or oxidizing atmosphere. Thus, the processing of magnetite ores is potentially possible without an additional process step. This integrated chemical and thermal conversion strategy enables efficient process intensification and supports the transition toward low-carbon ironmaking technologies. A schematic representation of this process configuration is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig.3 CLpre process description and principles

4 Thermodynamics of iron ore reduction within the CLpre process

4.1 Fundamentals

Thermodynamic analysis provides the fundamental framework for assessing the feasibility of iron ore reduction with syngas under defined process conditions. It allows for predicting equilibrium states based on temperature and gas composition, thereby identifying the conditions under which reduction reactions are energetically favorable. The feasibility of iron ore reduction is determined by the relative oxygen potentials of the gas and the metal oxide. The system reaches equilibrium when these oxygen potentials are equal. A redox reaction will occur only if the oxygen potential of the gas phase is lower than that of the oxide, thereby providing a driving force for oxygen release from the solid phase [9]. A general reaction for a metal-oxide oxidation is shown in Eq. 7.

Thermodynamically, the equilibrium between a metal (Me) and its oxide (MeO), using the mass action law is described by Eq.8:

$$K_p = \frac{a^{\text{MeO}}}{a^{\text{Me}} \cdot p_{\text{O}_2}} \quad (8)$$

The expression for equilibrium between the oxygen partial pressure and the equilibrium constant (activity of metal oxide and metal is equal to 1) is presented in Eq.9.

$$p_{\text{O}_2} = \frac{1}{K_p} \quad (9)$$

The standard Gibbs free energy change (ΔG) for the oxidation-reduction reaction is thermodynamically related to the equilibrium constant as shown in Eq. 10.

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln K_p \rightarrow \Delta G = -RT \ln p_{\text{O}_2}^* \quad (10)$$

This confirms that lower oxygen partial pressure corresponds to more negative ΔG° , thus thermodynamically favoring reduction. The equilibrium behavior of the Fe–O system is typically evaluated using a phase stability diagram that relates temperature and composition to the stability of iron oxide and metallic phases. The Fe–O phase diagram shown in Fig. 4 illustrates the relationships between

the different iron oxides (Fe_2O_3 , Fe_3O_4 , FeO) and the metallic phases of iron ($\alpha\text{-Fe}$ and $\gamma\text{-Fe}$) as a function of temperature and $\text{FeO}\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ weight percentage. Each phase is stable only within a specific range of temperature and composition, and the boundaries between regions correspond to equilibrium redox transitions. Thermodynamically, the system evolves to minimize its Gibbs free energy, and reduction occurs only when the oxygen potential of the gas phase is lower than that of the solid oxide. Conversely, if the gas-phase oxygen potential exceeds that of the oxide, oxidation becomes favorable and reduction is inhibited. Process control through the gas composition—specifically the $\text{H}_2/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and CO/CO_2 ratios and temperature is therefore essential to maintain the desired redox conditions during iron ore reduction. Thermodynamic tools such as the $\text{Fe}\text{-O}$ phase diagram are indispensable for defining operational boundaries and ensuring the targeted reduction degree under dynamic gas-phase conditions [9]. Thermodynamic tools such as the $\text{Fe}\text{-O}$ phase diagram are indispensable for defining operational boundaries and ensuring the targeted reduction degree under dynamic gas-phase conditions. CLpre experiments will be conducted in the 800–950 °C temperature range.

Fig. 4 Phase diagram of the $\text{Fe}\text{-O}$ system [10]

Iron oxide reduction proceeds via the indirect reduction mechanism in processes employing CO and H₂ as gaseous reductants. The stepwise conversion of iron oxides to metallic iron under reducing conditions is governed by temperature, gas composition and equilibrium behavior. The primary reduction reactions at $T > 570^\circ\text{C}$ are summarized as follows [9]:

1. Reduction of hematite to magnetite:

2. Reduction of magnetite to wüstite:

3. Reduction of wüstite to metallic iron:

At $T < 570^\circ\text{C}$, wüstite becomes thermodynamically unstable and hematite is reduced to magnetite and metallic iron $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \rightarrow \text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4 \rightarrow \text{Fe}$ by bypassing the wüstite phase.

The standard Gibbs free energy change (ΔG) determines the thermodynamic feasibility of these reactions and is defined by Eq.17.

$$\Delta G = \Delta H - T\Delta S \quad (17)$$

For a reaction to proceed spontaneously under isothermal conditions, ΔG must be negative. The relationship between Gibbs energy and the equilibrium constant K_p is expressed as:

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln K_p \quad (18)$$

The equilibrium constant is formulated in Eq.19.

$$K_p \left(\frac{\text{oxide}}{\text{reductant}} \right) = \exp \left(- \frac{\Delta G(\frac{\text{oxide}}{\text{reductant}})}{RT} \right) \quad (19)$$

When using CO gas mixtures for reduction, it is also necessary to consider the Boudouard equilibrium, which governs the conversion between carbon monoxide and carbon dioxide [11].

The thermochemical data reveal that CO-based reductions are generally exothermic or mildly endothermic, whereas H₂-based reductions—especially in the magnetite to wüstite step—require a significant thermal input. This difference impacts reactor heat management, particularly in systems where hydrogen is the dominant reductant. Thermodynamic tools such as the Baur–Glässner diagram, shown in Fig.5, provide phase stability boundaries for various iron oxide transformations. The diagram plots redox equilibria as a function of gas composition and temperature, enabling precise determination of the conditions required for a specific reduction step [11].

Fig. 5 Baur–Glässner diagram of the Fe–O–H₂ and Fe–O–C systems, including the Boudouard equilibrium (1 bar, carbon activity of 1)

To quantify the reducing potential of reducing gas used in iron ore reduction, the gas oxidation degree (GOD) is introduced. The GOD can be evaluated individually for hydrogen, carbon monoxide, as well as for a gas mixture, using Eq. 21–23 [12].

$$GOD = \frac{p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}{p_{\text{H}_2} + p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}} \quad (21)$$

$$GOD = \frac{pCO_2}{pCO + pCO_2} \tag{22}$$

$$GOD = \frac{pH_2O + pCO_2}{pH_2 + pH_2O + pCO + pCO_2} \tag{23}$$

A low GOD indicates a highly reducing environment, which is critical for the reduction of iron oxides to metallic Fe. Conversely, a high GOD reflects an oxidizing atmosphere and may shift the equilibrium toward iron oxide. Temperature plays a significant role. While higher temperatures accelerate reaction kinetics and diffusion through the solid matrix, they may also reduce the driving force for exothermic reactions by decreasing the negative value of ΔG as the entropy term $-T\Delta S$ increases. Therefore, optimization of the reduction process requires a careful balance between thermodynamic favorability and kinetic performance.

4.2 Thermodynamic considerations for the CLpre process

The CLpre process is based on the assumption that gasification of a biomass fuel with steam generates a gas which is oxidized via the circulating metal oxide (iron ore in the case of CLpre process). Thus, the highest theoretically achievable driving force for the reduction of iron ore corresponds to the gas composition obtained under pure gasification conditions without the presence of an oxygen carrier bed material. Typical product gas compositions obtained from gasification experiments at TU Wien pilot plant over several years and various feedstocks are shown in Fig. 6 [13].

Fig. 6 Product gas composition obtained from the gasification experiments with the advanced dual fluidized bed pilot plant at TU Wien

In this section, GOD is calculated for a typical gas composition consisting of 40% H₂, 20% CO and 20% CO₂ on a dry basis, with a water content of 40%. These assumptions result in a GOD value for the carbon species of 0.5 and 0.625 for the hydrogen species. The CLpre process aims to be conducted at >800 °C, within the typical operating range for a fluidized bed. The calculated GOD and the stable iron phase for the maximum driving force are shown in Fig. 7-9.

Fig. 7 Baur–Glössner diagram for the highest theoretically attainable driving force for the H-species during the CLpre process (GOD calculated according to Eq. 21)

Fig. 8 Baur–Glässner diagram for the highest theoretically attainable driving force for the C-species during the CLpre process (GOD calculated according to Eq. 22)

Fig. 9 Combined Baur–Glässner diagram for the highest theoretically attainable driving force for the C and H -species during the CLpre process (GOD calculated according to Eq. 23)

In conclusion, the thermodynamic framework for iron ore reduction with syngas is well established and highly favorable within the temperature range aimed for the CLpre process. The evaluation of the highest theoretically achievable driving force shows that the reduction potential of the obtained gas composition is placed in the wüstite area. However, it should be noted at this point that the reduction of a significant amount of iron ore to wüstite seems to be unlikely within the CLpre process, where a partial oxidation of the produced gas is aimed for to create the necessary heat for preheating of the introduced iron ore.

Thus, it can be concluded that hematite is most likely to be reduced to magnetite during the CLpre process, which results in a reduction degree of approx. 11%. Further reduction to wüstite may be possible, but seems to be unlikely.

5 Iron ore reduction kinetics

5.1 Fundamentals

The kinetics of iron oxide reduction describe the rate at which oxygen is removed from the oxide lattice during exposure to reducing gas atmospheres, resulting in the formation of metallic iron. Whereas thermodynamic analysis determines the conditions under which a reaction is energetically favorable, it does not provide information on the rate at which the transformation proceeds. Kinetic investigations are essential for assessing reaction rates and identifying the dominant rate-controlling mechanisms under varying process conditions. Several studies under different operating conditions have been conducted in this area, e.g. [12,14,15]. The reducibility of iron ores is strongly influenced by their microstructural properties, including particle size distribution, pore structure, crystal lattice structure and presence of gangue phases. These parameters affect the transport of gaseous reactants and the accessibility of reactive surfaces.

The kinetics of iron oxide reduction are controlled by a series of steps involving gas-phase transport, interfacial reaction and solid-state transformation [14]:

- Mass transfer of reducing gases from the bulk gas stream to the external particle surface: Reducing gases (CO , H_2) must first diffuse through a fluid boundary layer surrounding each iron oxide particle. This step is driven by the concentration gradient between the bulk gas phase and the surface of the solid. This boundary layer is continually disrupted in fluidized beds, rendering this step relatively fast and non-limiting under most industrial conditions.
- Adsorption of reducing gases onto the oxide surface: The reactive gas species form surface-bound intermediates through interactions with lattice oxygen. Adsorption behavior depends on temperature and the type of reductant. While CO may exhibit stronger adsorption, H_2 typically reacts faster due to its lower activation energy and higher diffusivity
- Surface reaction and removal of lattice oxygen: At the gas-solid interface, lattice oxygen is abstracted by the adsorbed reductants, forming CO_2 or H_2O and leaving behind iron nuclei. This redox step initiates the transformation of iron oxides with the overall reaction rate dependent on the bond strength of the oxygen atoms within the oxide crystal lattice. In the context of a limiting phase interface reaction, the amount of oxygen removed per unit time can be expressed as follows:

$$\frac{dn_{O,H_2}}{dt} = A * k_{H_2}(T) * (p_{H_2} - p_{H_2}^*) \quad (24)$$

$$\frac{dn_{O,CO}}{dt} = A * k_{CO}(T) * (p_{CO} - p_{CO}^*) \quad (25)$$

- Desorption and evacuation of gaseous by-products: Once formed, gaseous products (H₂O, CO₂) must desorb from the oxide surface and diffuse out of the particle. These product gases may partially inhibit further reaction if not efficiently removed, as their accumulation near the surface reduces the local driving force for reduction.
- Solid-state transport and phase rearrangement: The transformation of oxides into lower oxidation states or metallic iron involves structural reconfiguration of the crystalline lattice and migration of metal ions and vacancies. This is particularly relevant in the FeO-to-Fe transition, which can be diffusion-controlled due to the formation of dense iron layers that act as diffusion barriers.
- Diffusion through internal pores: At the surface, the gas molecules enter the porous structure of the ore particle. Diffusion occurs through macropores (≥50 nm) and micropores (≤2 nm), both of which are formed during ore preparation or generated during reduction. Resistance to mass transport increases with tortuosity, pore constriction, and reduced porosity. This step is critical for ensuring reactants reach the active reaction front within the particle.
- Back-diffusion of reaction products to the bulk phase: Final product gases must exit through the pore system and boundary layer to re-enter the bulk gas stream. Delays in this stage may influence local equilibrium and slow reaction rates.

The rate-limiting step among these depends on temperature, gas composition, ore morphology and reduction extent. At lower temperatures, the surface reaction may dominate, whereas at higher temperatures and in later stages of reduction, internal diffusion or solid-state migration often becomes rate-controlling. Depending on the prevailing conditions, the overall rate of iron ore reduction may be governed by one of three kinetic regimes: a chemically controlled regime, where the interfacial reaction at the oxide surface is rate-limiting; a diffusion-controlled regime, in which mass transport through product layers or porous structures dominates or a mixed-control regime, where both surface reaction and diffusive resistance contribute significantly to the overall rate. Hydrogen reduction typically exhibits faster kinetics than CO, primarily due to its superior diffusivity and lower activation energy. This makes H₂ advantageous in low to moderate temperatures, while CO may become more effective at elevated temperatures above 850 °C[11]. These observations emphasize the importance of characterizing both the structural evolution of the solid and the mass transport behavior of the gas

phase when designing and optimizing iron ore reduction systems. Accurate modeling of these phenomena, most notably through the shrinking core model (SCM), enables quantitative prediction of reduction behavior under industrial conditions. The SCM conceptualizes the iron oxide particle as consisting of an unreacted core that diminishes over time, surrounded by a shell of partially or fully reduced product. This model assumes that the reaction front moves inward from the surface as reduction progresses, with the outer layers representing reduced material and the core maintaining its original composition. Fig. 10 shows that the shrinking core model includes gas diffusion through the product layer, surface reaction at the unreacted interface and diffusion of product gases back to the surface. Depending on system conditions, any of these steps may dominate the overall rate [11].

Fig. 10 Schematic of the shrinking-core model [16]

Experimental studies using thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) also provide validation for this model. SEM imaging frequently reveals core-shell morphologies in partially reduced particles, while TGA confirms time-dependent mass loss consistent with inward-moving reaction fronts. The gas-based reduction of iron oxides is a complex process involving multiple solid phases and gas-solid reactions. Zugliano et al. [17] proposed a phase reduction behavior model to describe the reduction of iron ore with syngas in a direct reduction reactor.

Fig.11 Three kinetic phases determined during experimental investigations at TU Wien [17]

TU Wien has developed a kinetic model, which divides the iron ore reduction into three phases [11,18-19]. The model focuses on the reduction of hematite by a CO and H₂ mixture and is based on gas-solid reaction kinetics. A combined approach of literature-based kinetic methods and laboratory-scale experimental investigations was used to characterize the reduction behavior. Figure 11 illustrates the oxygen removal rate during the reduction of iron oxide as a function of time. The y-axis represents the oxygen removal rate, expressed as dY/dt , quantifying the amount of oxygen removed per mole of iron atoms per minute. The x-axis displays the reaction time t in minutes. In this model, the reduction proceeds through three distinct stages, each corresponding to one of the iron oxide transformation steps:

- Stage I: the initial reaction step is limited by the transport of gas-phase products such as H₂O or CO₂ from the surface of iron ore particles.
- Stage II: this phase represents the intermediate stage between the gas-transport-limited regime and the solid-state-controlled regime.
- Stage III: the final stage, the reaction is limited by phase boundary kinetics and solid-state diffusion within the material.

The reacting particle is surrounded by pores and consists of smaller grains. The reduction proceeds uniformly within these grains. Kinetic analyses indicate that the overall reaction rate is not

governed by pore diffusion limitations. The kinetics of Phase I and Phase III reduction can be formulated as follows:

$$\frac{dY}{dt} = \dot{Y} = \left(\frac{d}{d_0}\right)^r * Y^c * K * \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right) * \left[\left(\frac{p_{H2} - p_{H2}^*}{p_0}\right)^m + A_1 * \left(\frac{p_{CO} - p_{CO}^*}{p_0}\right)^n\right] \quad (26)$$

This expression allows for quantifying the fractional reduction rate under non-isothermal, multicomponent gas conditions. The kinetic parameters associated with the reduction rate, rate constant K and activation energy E are dependent on the physicochemical characteristics of the specific iron ore. Their determination requires empirical evaluation through isothermal reduction experiments, typically performed in controlled batch reactor systems to account for ore-specific variables such as porosity, grain structure and reactivity under defined gas-phase conditions [17].

In summary, the kinetics of iron oxide reduction with syngas are governed by phase transitions, microstructural evolution and rate-limiting mass transport mechanisms. Control over gas composition, temperature and reactor hydrodynamics is essential to avoid premature dense layer formation and ensure uniform reduction. Optimizing these parameters enables high metallization rates in fluidized bed and chemical looping configurations aligned with thermodynamic feasibility. Fluidized-bed and CLC systems must optimize temperature, gas composition and residence time to avoid diffusion-limited regimes and ensure high metallization rates. Understanding and controlling these kinetic parameters is essential to fully understand the thermodynamic potential of syngas-based ironmaking.

5.2 Kinetic considerations for the CLpre process

Since it has been found during the thermodynamic investigations in this report that the achievable reduction during the CLpre process will mainly be the reduction from hematite to magnetite, which probably corresponds to the first kinetic phase in Fig. 11 and Eq. 26, the kinetics during the CLpre process are potentially fast.

Feilmayr et al. [12] and Sturn et al. [19] conducted two studies where the kinetics of the first reduction phase were investigated at 10 bar pressurized conditions. The investigations were conducted in a fluidized bed kinetic apparatus with silica sand and diluted iron ore. The authors found a phase boundary reaction limitation under these conditions. Spreitzer and Schenk [20] conducted a literature review

focusing on H₂ direct reduction. However, they also summarized some studies with CO as a reducing agent. In general, phase boundary limitations are mainly identified as the rate-limiting step during the iron ore reduction in this review study.

However, Habermann et al. [21] investigated the rate-limiting step of the first reduction phase in a fluidized bed kinetic apparatus operated under atmospheric pressure and with silica sand diluted iron ore at 780 °C (gas components: H₂, CO and CO₂ with N₂). Even under conditions where the iron ore was diluted, the authors concluded that the first phase is “*controlled by the transport of the reducing gas from the bubble phase of the fluidized bed to the iron ore particle and the transport of product gas from the particle to the bubble phase*”. This means that the supply of the reducing gas and fluid dynamic conditions are the limiting step for the conditions under atmospheric pressure and typical fluidized bed conditions.

Thus, for the CLpre process and the expected achievable reduction degrees, the available amount of reducing gas is most likely the limiting step during ore reduction in the fuel reactor (FR), which operates as a typical bubbling bed under atmospheric pressure.

Consequently, for further considerations, no typical kinetic limitations are assumed at the moment. In the course of the project, this assumption may change, because the actual kinetics is highly dependent on, e.g., iron ore type, gas composition and temperature.

Symbols

A	Reaction surface area of solid (oxide particle)	[m ²]
a	Activity of component i	[-]
c	Reaction order	[-]
d/d ₀	Ratio of current to reference oxide sphere diameter	[-]
dn _o /dt	Oxygen removed via reduction with species i	[mol/s]
dY/dt	Reduction rate	[mol _O /mol _{Fe} /min]
E	Activation energy	[J/mol]
ΔG°	Gibbs free energy	[J/mol]

ΔH	Enthalpy change	[J]
K	Pre-exponential factor in the Arrhenius term	[1/s]
k_i	Kinetic rate constant of gas-solid reaction with species i	[mol/m ² *Pa*s]
K_p	Equilibrium constant	[-]
m	Reaction order	[-]
n	Reaction order	[-]
P^*	Partial pressure of species in equilibrium state	[Pa]
P_0	Total pressure	[Pa]
p_{CO}	Actual partial pressure of CO	[Pa]
P_{H_2}	Actual partial pressure of H ₂	[Pa]
p_{O_2}	Partial pressure of oxygen	[Pa]
r	Empirical size exponent	[-]
R	Gas constant	[J/mol*K]
ΔS	Entropy change	[J/K]
T	Temperature	[K]
R	Universal gas constant	[J/mol*K]
μ_f	Dynamic viscosity of fluid	[kg/m*s]
Y	Fractional reduction	[-]
y	Non-stoichiometry of wuestite and magnetite	[-]
α	Oxygen-to-metal ratio in metal oxide	[-]
δ	Non-stoichiometry of hematite	[-]

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